

Concentrating and sequestering biomolecules in condensates: impact on plant biology

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Highlight

Growing examples of protein condensation phenomena prompt the re-evaluation of their functions in cells. We hereby discuss the possible implications of protein condensation for plant biology.

1 **Introduction**

2 Biomolecules can exist in a variety of forms, ranging from single entities to mesoscale assemblies akin to
3 small organelles, also known as “biomolecular condensates”. The formation of biomolecular condensates is
4 expedited by phase separation, in which molecules demix to form dilute and condensed phases. Phase
5 separation results in concentrating or sequestering certain molecules, thus altering their abundance or other
6 features in the phases and in this way inhibiting or promoting biochemical reactions. Here, we discuss recent
7 research implicating biomolecular condensates in the regulation of biochemical reactions in plants.

8

9 Condensation can modulate biochemical pathways

10 The dissonance in terms of properties between small molecular assemblies with definite stoichiometries and
11 mesoscale assemblies of heterogenous size, molecular mass, composition, and presumably stochastic
12 stoichiometry prompts a reassessment of basic organizational principles in cells. Despite this stochasticity,
13 mesoscale assemblies output highly selective biochemical reactions underlying cellular- and organismal-level
14 responses at precise locations and times (Pappu, 2020).

15 Phase separation is likely central to the formation of some mesoscale assemblies; we discuss further
16 its biophysical nature in **Box 1**. Here, we define phase separation as an abrupt state transition whereby
17 molecules with a propensity to stick to one another will separate from their solvent into distinct assemblies
18 forming quasi-1-dimensional compartments (on linear molecules, e.g., DNA), pseudo-2-dimensional patches
19 (on membranes), or bodies (e.g., in the cytoplasm). We refer to all these mesoscale assemblies, which can
20 form anywhere in the cell, using the umbrella term “condensates”. Although condensates can arise through
21 liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) their liquidity can be lost under certain microenvironmental conditions,
22 modifications on their components, or when given enough time to age. Hence condensates can attain less
23 fluid but more gel- or solid-like material properties, the transitions being of utmost importance for their
24 functionality. Below, we summarise examples highlighting how condensates steer plant physiology by
25 modulating certain biochemical reactions (see also **Box 2**, and **Supplemental information**).

26 During development, some of the transcription factors regulating auxin outputs known as AUXIN
27 RESPONSE FACTORS (ARFs), undergo phase separation (Powers *et al.*, 2019). *Arabidopsis* has 22 ARFs,
28 with most containing an N-terminal DNA binding domain, a middle part with an intrinsically disordered region
29 (IDR), and a C-terminal domain mediating ARF-ARF and ARF-auxin interactions (**Box 1**). For a review on
30 ARF functions, we refer the reader to (Cancé *et al.*, 2022). ARF7 and ARF19 are nuclear in cells near the
31 root tip, thereby involved in the transcription of auxin-responsive genes (Powers *et al.*, 2019). Far from the
32 meristematic cells of the root tip, however, these proteins form cytoplasmic condensates hampering nuclear
33 localisation, and in this way mitigating auxin responsiveness. Condensation of the ARFs is mediated by a
34 glutamine-rich prion-like domain (PLD; **Box 1**) within their IDR, while the C-terminal domain also contributes
35 to the condensation perhaps by facilitating intermolecular interactions between ARFs. ARF condensation in
36 the cytoplasm allows specific cells to get desensitised to auxin when they need to e.g., when they function
37 as auxin conduits that channel auxin to other cells. When these cells need to regain responsiveness to auxin
38 (e.g., to initiate lateral roots), the ARF-condensates undergo dissolution through an unknown mechanism and
39 re-enter the nucleus.

40 Intriguingly, ARF-condensates are not typical non-stoichiometric assemblies as they form a
41 stoichiometric shell (ARF-ARF) at their periphery. This local stoichiometry may play an important role in
42 modulating ARF-condensate permeability to additional ARF molecules or other, as yet unidentified,
43 components. In this respect, ARF-condensates are reminiscent of proteinaceous conserved bacterial micro-
44 compartments (BMCs) engulfing a cohort of different enzymes to facilitate biochemical reactions (Al-Husini
45 *et al.*, 2018).

46 Apart from developmental fate decisions, condensates' reversibility would be perfectly fitted for
47 oscillatory biochemical outputs. The EARLY FLOWERING 3 (ELF3) is a transcription factor involved in diurnal
48 rhythms. Increased temperatures induce the formation of ELF3-condensates in the nucleus, a process
49 mediated by the ELF3-PLD (**Box 2, panels A and B**) (Jung *et al.*, 2020). ELF3-condensates preclude ELF3
50 molecules from binding their targets on DNA. At low temperatures, however, ELF3-condensates dissolve
51 thereby derepressing ELF3-dependent transcription of genes inhibiting flowering. Noteworthy, the ELF3-PLD
52 which mediates condensation, displays a variable length and composition among natural populations or
53 species, with longer PLDs richer in glutamate promoting condensation. Hence increased condensation of
54 ELF3 homologs is translated to accelerated flowering in warmer climates. Intriguingly, the yeast
55 Polyadenylate-binding protein (Pab1) is exquisitely sensitive to temperature. A 10°C increase accelerates
56 Pab1 condensation and likely its activity by >300-fold. This increase is much greater than, for example,
57 changes in ion currents for thermosensitive ion channels, which are also tuned for temperature sensing
58 (Sengupta and Garrity, 2013). Therefore, the evolution of condensates as environmental sensors may thus
59 offer a remedy for the non-linear scaling-up of biochemical reaction rates.

60 **Condensates as catalysts**

61 Recent studies began to shed light on the significance of condensates for enhancing enzymatic reactions in
62 plants that could be achieved through one of the three major mechanisms or their combinations (summarized
63 in **Box 2, panel C**). In most algae and hornwort plants, the CO₂-assimilating enzyme Rubisco condenses
64 within a chloroplast organelle called pyrenoid, as a part of a CO₂-concentrating process. In *Chlamydomonas*
65 *reinhardtii*, Rubisco undergoes LLPS with the IDR-rich protein EPYC1 (Essential Pyrenoid Component 1) to
66 form a pyrenoid (Rosenzweig *et al.*, 2017). Whether co-condensation of Rubisco with EPYC1 lowers K_M for
67 CO₂ or increases k_{cat} of Rubisco remains unknown.

68 Lying upstream of CO₂ assimilation in photosynthetic organisms is CO₂ sensing that initiates a
69 plethora of signalling pathways central to organismal adaptation to changing CO₂ concentrations. One
70 potential CO₂ sensing mechanism shared by fungi and plants is a direct, CO₂ concentration-dependent,
71 activation of a unique group of PP2C phosphatases (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). These enzymes are distinguished
72 by the presence of serine/threonine-enriched IDR, which renders them phase-separating and forming liquid-
73 like, catalytically active condensates in response to elevated CO₂. Further work is required to demonstrate
74 the physiological relevance of this elegant mechanism coupling enzyme concentration and activation, e.g.,
75 in the context of stomatal closure.

76 The regulation of the *Arabidopsis* floral repressor *FLC* and other developmental genes relies on the
77 conserved co-transcriptional mechanism of RNA 3'-end processing (*viz.* cleavage and polyadenylation). In
78 the case of *FLC*, 3'-end processing requires the RNA-binding intrinsically disordered protein FCA (Flowering
79 Control Locus A), which forms nuclear condensates in a process dependent on the coiled-coil protein FLL2
80 (Fang *et al.*, 2019). The FCA bodies are enriched for the enzymatic components of the 3'-end processing.
81 An important next step would be to elucidate whether in FCA bodies the 3'-end processing machinery

82 becomes more active or whether FCA bodies simply serve as a storage depot for the components of this
83 machinery.

84 The phosphorylation activity of the evolutionarily conserved SNF1/AMPK/SnRK1 protein kinase plays
85 a central role in metabolic response to declined energy levels under nutritional and environmental stresses.
86 Our recent study revealed a direct association of *Arabidopsis* SnRK1 catalytic subunit isoforms $\alpha 1$ and $\alpha 2$
87 with Tudor Staphylococcal Nuclease (TSN) in heat-induced stress granules (SGs) (Gutierrez-Beltran *et al.*,
88 2021). TSN serves as a scaffold for recruiting many client proteins to SGs, whereas its deficiency represses
89 both SG recruitment and kinase activity of SnRK1 α . These data suggest that SG assembly favours SnRK1
90 activation through an unknown mechanism.

91 Interestingly, one condensate may promote some and inhibit other biochemical reactions. The
92 condensate formed in response to biotic stress by the NON-EXPRESSOR OF PATHOGENESIS RELATED
93 GENES 1 (NPR1) counteracts effector-triggered immunity (ETI) mediated by salicylic acid (SA) in uninfected
94 cells (Zavaliev *et al.*, 2020). ETI often leads to cellular suicide, which restricts pathogen spread beyond the
95 invasion site. In the adjacent non-infected tissues, systemic acquired resistance (SAR) prevents extensive
96 damage through NPR1. Three redox-sensitive IDRs punctuated with cysteines in NPR1, upon infection and
97 in the presence of SA mediate NPR1 condensation in the cytoplasm forming the so-called "SINCs" (SA-
98 induced NPR1 condensates). The SINCs sequester the Cullin 3 RING E3 ligase (CRL3) adaptor promoting
99 its activity, while sequestration of other positive regulators of ETI leads to their sequestration and inhibition.

00 **Perspective**

01 We summarize some outstanding questions in **Box 3**. To further explore and utilize condensates as catalysts
02 of biochemical reactions in plants, we should prioritise the non-invasive measurements of reaction rates in
03 the dense versus the dilute phases in living cells. In the same context, the composition of condensates, their
04 internal organization, the reaction specificities in their different parts, and their regulated dissolution are
05 research directions that need to be further explored. In the long run, these advances together with
06 engineering more efficient phase-separating enzymes, condensate-targeting drugs, or probes, as well as
07 transgenic plants with optimised performance of enzymatically active condensates, will enrich an arsenal of
08 tools for artificial manipulation of plant development and resilience. In conclusion, many plant enzymes
09 evolved to occur within or depending on biomolecular condensates, under a selection pressure that likely
10 favoured plant adaptation. As a cautionary note, the current model assuming low-affinity unspecific
11 interactions among IDRs to be the major mechanism underpinning biogenesis of biomolecular condensates
12 has been recently criticised (Musacchio, 2022). An alternative model assumes that it is actually site-specific
13 interactions that may be the key drivers of this process.

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1 **BOX 1. An introduction to the molecular grammar of phase separation.**

2 **Figure 1**

3 The past few years have experienced tremendous progress in the evolution of a molecular grammar that
4 underpins phase separation. Protein and RNA are polymers with attractive groups known as “stickers” that
5 form non-covalent and mainly weak interactions. At certain concentrations which are determined by various
6 factors (e.g., temperature, redox state, pH), interactions are enabled among intra- or intermolecular stickers
7 (e.g., protein 1 - protein 2 interaction on the cartoon). When reaching a system-specific threshold
8 concentration ($C_{threshold}$), the whole system undergoes a transition into at least two or more phases, a process
9 known as phase separation. Here, the dense phases are often referred to as condensates. Stickers are
10 connected by “spacers” that regulate the density transitions by orienting stickers. The “stickiness” (or
11 multivalency) depends on the attraction between charged residues, dipoles, or aromatic groups that are
12 usually provided by the so-called “intrinsically disordered regions” (IDRs, one class are the prion-like domains
13 noted as PrLD, while both belong to the class of low complexity regions). IDRs lack a defined structure and
14 thus can easily expose their stickers. As a cautionary note, proteins that undergo phase separation (e.g.,
15 LLPS) are usually enriched with IDRs, but many examples show that folded domains or nucleic acids, also
16 mediate phase separation [e.g., protein 3 with RNA binding domain (RBD) in the cartoon]. Condensates that
17 have formed by LLPS can display properties of water droplets, such as sphericity, to reduce surface tension,
18 along with increased density and viscosity due to the increased internal concentration. Condensates may
19 also exchange molecules with the surrounding dilute phase. Furthermore, some molecules function as
20 “scaffolds” for the condensation process (much like “nucleators”), and likely are recruited first in “pre-
21 condensation” assemblies. Yet, other proteins are recruited to the condensate through multivalent
22 interactions with scaffolds, including RNA binding proteins (RBPs) interacting with RNA molecules. These
23 molecules are called “clients” and may affect condensates by regulating their material properties, e.g., liquid-
24 to-solid transitions or formation of aggregates and filaments at high concentrations. On the top right, we depict
25 domain organization of ARF7 and ARF19 as examples of phase separating proteins (Powers *et al.*, 2019).
26 For an overview of ARFs architectures we refer the reader to (Cancé *et al.*, 2022). Other ARFs (e.g., ARF5,
27 6, and 8) have significantly shorter IDRs and PrLDs and likely do not condensate. PTMs, post-translational
28 modifications.

29

BOX 2. Examples of condensates and models for enzymatic regulation by condensates.

Figure 2

A. Selected examples of condensates, along with their localization, and stimuli involved in their formation. Condensates on the cytoskeleton, Golgi, and ER have not been identified in plants yet. For condensates not discussed in the text (GDACs, SOSEKI, and photobodies) we provide references in the supplemental information summarizing major condensates in plants.

B. Condensates can pause certain pathways by sequestering e.g., transcription factors away from DNA. Example of transcriptional downregulation by ELF3, LUX or ELF4/GI condensates (Jung *et al.*, 2020). See also supplemental information.

C. Reaction rates in the condensed and dilute phases cannot be equivalent for several reasons. (a, mass action) Condensates may alter reaction rates by changing the diffusion and local concentration of an enzyme, as well as its substrate(s), product(s), co-factor(s), inhibitor(s), or even competing enzyme(s). Thus, condensates may enhance reactions through increased concentrations of enzymes and/or substrates. This is especially important when the concentrations of the molecules involved are low.

(b, altered environment) The chemical composition of the solvent may change upon condensation creating a microenvironment with altered electrostatics, permeability, and hydrophobicity that will in turn influence substrate binding (K_M). Changes in permeability could in principle restrict the entry of inhibitory molecules into the condensate.

(c, structural switches) Many enzymes are recruited to condensates as scaffolds or clients (see also Box 1 for definitions), through multivalent hetero- or homotypic interactions that may evoke conformational changes affecting substrate K_M . In the example, a scaffold recruits the client enzyme and at the same time undergoes structural modifications enabling enzyme concentration in a confined space, thus enhancing its activity.

The aforementioned mechanisms can be used in a combination, further enhancing the specificity and efficiency of single or multi-step reactions (Peeples and Rosen, 2021; Zhang *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, some enzymatic reactions within condensates or on the interface of two phases might sustain condensate material properties, functionality, and longevity, as exemplified by ATP hydrolysis (Linsenmeier *et al.*, 2022).

56 **BOX 3. Outstanding questions**

57 • How do condensates interact with one another and how this could affect biochemical reactions? In animals,
58 for example, ZNFX1 and WAGO4 transition to perinuclear condensates termed Z granules, immediately
59 adjacent to P granules (Phillips *et al.*, 2012). In adult germline cells, Z granules associate with another type
60 of bodies, the Mutator foci that contain proteins involved in RNA silencing.

61 • What are the sequence determinants (including short linear motives) in phase-separating proteins that
62 define such behavior in plants? One route to addressing this question is to examine homologous condensates
63 found in related organisms that live at, for instance, high versus low temperatures when the stimulus for
64 condensation is temperature. For example, a recent study exploited the natural variation in the IDR of FLOE1
65 condensates in seeds to suggest that FLOE1 condensation propensity can regulate germination timing
66 (Dorone *et al.*, 2021). Such approaches may spur new thinking about the molecular grammar underpinning
67 condensate formation *in vivo*. From agronomical perspective, getting insights into the molecular grammar of
68 condensation could allow the selection or introduction of beneficial traits.

69 • How is the conformation and activity of an enzyme altered when entering a condensate *in vivo*? Yet, it is
70 unclear what the conformation of proteins (and RNAs) that enter a condensed state is. In condensates,
71 proteins may either get protected from degradation or get degraded more; this has also been suggested for
72 RNA molecules (Poudyal *et al.*, 2021). A less folded state may allow stickers to explore their surrounding
73 space and find favourable partner stickers, thereby mediating condensation propensity. The increased rigidity
74 in a folded state could conflict with the need for stickers to explore their surroundings and is, therefore,
75 kinetically disadvantageous (Day *et al.*, 2021). *In vivo* evidence in support of results of increased activity in
76 condensates heretofore obtained only for recombinant proteins or *in vitro* reconstituted condensates is
77 lacking (Peeples and Rosen, 2021)

78 • What is the actual composition and function of multilayered condensates such as ARF-condensates, and
79 how each layer contributes to activity regulation? In humans, single-phase condensates formed by phospho-
80 FMRP (Fragile X mental retardation protein) and CAPRIN1 homogeneously recruit RNA and the deadenylase
81 CNOT7. By contrast, two-phase condensates formed by FMRP and phospho-CAPRIN1 concentrate RNA
82 and CNOT7 into distinct inner and outer phases, respectively (Kim *et al.*, 2019). Despite spatial segregation,
83 deadenylating activity was higher in the two-phase system than in the one-phase system, suggesting that
84 enrichment does not always lead to higher activity.